

Developing an integral data assimilation approach for nuclear data evaluation

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ABSTRACT

Based on various approaches presented in the literature, a comprehensive Bayesian framework was developed, taking into account the different sources of uncertainty and biases for the assimilation of integral experimental data. Combining existing data assimilation approaches, the method makes use of a data-driven Gaussian Process (GP) bias model within a fully marginalized Markov-Chain Monte-Carlo (MCMC) inference that handles a broad set of nuisance parameters via Latin Hypercube sampling (LHS) marginalization. This end-to-end treatment offers a precise way to include large integral-experiment databases in nuclear data evaluation. To illustrate the approach, we apply it to a minimal, analytically tractable test case: the average prompt-neutron multiplicity $\bar{\nu}_p$ of ^{235}U is calibrated against nine critical UOX benchmark experiments, enabling a direct comparison with the conventional generalized-least-squares (GLS) solution. A 2000-step MCMC chain satisfies standard convergence diagnostics. Posterior predictive checks confirm bias reduction between calculation and experimental results. The resulting posterior yields a normalization factor ν of **0.9989** (-0.11% relative to the prior) and reduces the relative uncertainty of $\bar{\nu}_p$ from **0.5%** to **0.16%**. When combined with the delayed-neutron component $\bar{\nu}_d$, the total multiplicity $\bar{\nu}_{tot} = 2.434$ aligns with the JEFF-4 evaluation and lies well within the confidence intervals of the Neutron Data Standards 2018.

Keywords: nuclear data, Bayesian statistics, integral experiments, Markov-Chain Monte-Carlo

1. INTRODUCTION

In most nuclear engineering and physics applications such as reactor design, a dominant source of uncertainty often stems from the underlying nuclear data (ND). Improving measurements and evaluations is therefore a primary focus for reducing overall uncertainty in nuclear applications. In particular, assimilating integral experiments by leveraging comprehensive databases can markedly reduce ND uncertainties for selected isotopes, reaction channels, and energy intervals where microscopic measurements can be scarce or have significant systematic uncertainties [1, 2]. The evaluation process, whether analytical [3] or sample-based [4], is commonly formulated in a Bayesian framework. Integral Data Assimilation (IDA) is a central component of that evaluation process [5, 6], but has also been used for direct ND adjustment [7] like our case study. Deterministic neutronics codes can exhibit biases arising from modeling choices and discretizations; stochastic Monte-Carlo (MC) codes are commonly used as reference simulations, but they are computationally costly, limiting their use in sampling-based uncertainty propagation. This motivates combining deterministic simulations with learned bias corrections to enable extensive sampling. The Bayesian framework used for ND evaluation is here applied to assimilate integral experimental data, building on the approach of well established codes such as SAMMY and its SAMINT module [8] or CONRAD [9]. Sample-based Bayesian approaches to integral data assimilation are now well established. Unlike GLS methods, they require no linearity assumption, accommodate non-Gaussian parameter distributions, and characterize the full posterior rather than a Gaussian approximation around its mode. These properties make them appropriate for problems involving threshold effects, resonance parameters, or other strongly non-linear responses, although at a computational cost that limits applicability to moderate dimensionality. However, the treatment of

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deterministic model discrepancy remains a challenge: common practice either inflates experimental uncertainties to absorb unmodeled biases or relies on prescribed correction factors. The framework presented here addresses this limitation by embedding a data-driven bias correction model trained on discrepancies between deterministic and MC reference calculations directly within the likelihood function. This allows systematic computational errors to be learned and propagated coherently alongside experimental and technological uncertainties, rather than treated as an external correction or absorbed into other variance terms.

2. SOURCES OF UNCERTAINTY AND BIASES

2.1. Nuclear data

Since the JEFF-3 series, explicit covariance information has been incorporated into evaluated nuclear data files, enabling rigorous uncertainty quantification [10]. These covariance matrices encode multiple correlated uncertainty sources: experimental, normalization, model, and processing, allowing them to be naturally integrated as prior information in a Bayesian adjustment framework.

Covariance-development efforts have prioritized isotopes and reaction channels most impactful to reactor applications (notably ^{235}U , ^{238}U , and ^{239}Pu) for neutronics and safety studies through the so-called HPRP (High Priority Request List) [11]. In a Bayesian adjustment, evaluated covariance matrices can be naturally integrated as prior information, allowing integral-experiment likelihoods to update this prior information into a posterior within the same probabilistic framework. In our simple case involving the single parameter \bar{v}_p of ^{235}U at the thermal point $E_{th} = 0.0253 \text{ eV}$, this reduces to a simple prior distribution $P(\bar{v}_p)$. More precisely, we integrate a normalization factor ν associated with \bar{v}_p . This factor follows a normal distribution $\mathcal{N}(1, \sigma_\nu^2)$ with $\sigma_\nu = 0.5\%$ the relative prior uncertainty chosen to demonstrate the methodology.

2.2. Experimental and technological data

Critical benchmarks are well-characterized integral experiments (critical assemblies, benchmarks, or reactor configurations) used to validate and adjust nuclear data and neutronics methods. They provide measured integral observables (most commonly k_{eff} , reaction rates, spectral indices, reactivity coefficients, post-irradiated experiments) under controlled geometry, material composition, and operating conditions. Nine benchmarks were used in the qualification of the APOLLO2.8.3 version [12] based on JEFF-3.1.1 and used for industrial applications. Those benchmarks and the results associated with them were used in this work and are summarized in Table I along with the relevant parameters involved in the bias correction model, pitch being the distance between two rods within an assembly, R_{mod} the volumic moderation ratio, Q the slowing-down ratio at $E_c = 4 \text{ eV}$ and C_B the boron concentration in the moderator in *ppm*.

While the experimental uncertainties can be integrated directly into the likelihood, "nuisance" parameters are model or experimental quantities that are not of primary interest (not the target nuclear data) but nevertheless affect the integral observables used in data assimilation. They must be accounted for because their uncertainty biases or inflates the inferred nuclear data adjustments. It is possible to integrate these different technological parameters into experimental covariance matrices under certain assumptions and to perform the adjustment analytically or, conversely, to treat these uncertainties independently using marginalization methods [13]. The technological parameters (θ) associated with our benchmarks are listed in Table II.

Let x be a nuclear parameter, y a set of experimental data points and θ a set of "nuisance" parameters. In a marginalized adjustment, we explicitly account for nuisance parameters θ , leading to the marginalized posterior distribution

Table I. UOX critical benchmarks: calculation-experiment biases and uncertainties with JEFF-3.1.1

Benchmark	Pitch (cm)	R_{mod}	Q	C_B	C/E-1 (pcm)	σ_E (pcm)
EPICURE UH1.2	1.26	1.25	0.51	569	+468	± 316
CAMELEON GC	1.26	1.8	0.57	610	+867	± 381
CRISTO3	0.96	0.45	0.37	0.0	+518	± 682
MISTRAL1	1.32	1.75	0.53	294.2	-100	± 376
CRISTO1	1.86	5.46	0.89	750	-129	± 381
CRISTO2 $C_B = 832$ ppm	1.58	3.56	0.76	832	-183	± 371
CRISTO2 "large"	1.71	4.40	0.79	672.5	-82	± 371
ZPR HIC steel cladding	1.24	0.96	0.51	0	+120	± 481
ZPR HIC aluminium cladding	1.24	0.96	0.37	0	-389	± 481

Table II. Technological parameters and their associated uncertainties

Technological parameters (θ)	Symbol	Uncertainty
^{235}U enrichment	N_U	0.3%
Fuel density	ρ_{comb}	0.3%
Fuel radius	R_{comb}	0.1%
Outer cladding radius	$R_{g,ext}$	0.2%
Lattice pitch	p	0.002 cm
Fuel impurities	N_B	1 ppm (natural boron)
Oxygen in UO_2	N_O	0.2%
Water density	$\rho_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$	0.01%

$$P(x | y) = \int P(x | y, \theta) P(\theta | y) d\theta, \quad (1)$$

This integral is estimated using the LHS method [14], which ensures coverage of the input-parameter space with fewer samples than plain Monte-Carlo by imposing stratification while preserving statistical properties [15]. Among the marginalized parameters, perturbation analysis identifies ^{235}U enrichment and fuel impurities as the dominant contributors to posterior uncertainty, accounting for 78–98% depending on the benchmark.

2.3. Deterministic neutron transport code biases

Deterministic transport codes exhibit systematic discrepancies relative to Monte Carlo references, arising from spatial and angular discretization, self-shielding approximations, and incomplete treatment of resonance interference effects. These model deficiencies are distinct from nuclear data uncertainties and, if unaccounted for, can bias the posterior. Common approaches either absorb such discrepancies into inflated experimental uncertainties or apply benchmark-specific correction factors; both obscure the physical origin of the bias. In this work, a GP model is trained on APOLLO2–TRIPOLI4 residuals to

learn the systematic component of deterministic bias as a function of system characteristics. A related approach using Gram-Schmidt orthonormalization was previously developed by one of the authors [16]; the present GP formulation, developed by Terrazzoni [17], offers a continuous correction across the parameter space.

For each experiment i and parameter set (ν, θ) , a deterministic neutron simulation is run in the following way:

$$f_{monte-carlo}(\nu, \theta) = f_{deterministic}(\nu, \theta) + b(\nu, \theta) \quad (2)$$

where $b(\nu, \theta)$ is the bias estimated by the trained model.

3. COMPLETE METHODOLOGY

The complete methodology used in this work is resumed in Table III.

- ν : the normalization factor associated with $\bar{\nu}_p$, with probability density function $p(\nu)$,
- θ : nuisance parameters (technological) with joint distribution $p(\theta)$,
- y : experimental results from critical benchmarks, associated with the bias model,
- q the Metropolis-Hastings [18] proposition function.

Table III. Full algorithm: Metropolis-Hastings with marginalization

1. Initialization of $\nu^{(0)}$
2. For $k=1$ to N :
 - a) Propose $\nu' \sim q(\nu'|\nu^{(k-1)})$
 - b) Estimate $p(y|\nu')$ by LHS marginalization
 - c) Compute the acceptance ratio:

$$\alpha = \min \left(1, \frac{p(\nu') \cdot p(y|\nu') \cdot q(\nu|\nu')}{p(\nu) \cdot p(y|\nu) \cdot q(\nu|\nu')} \right)$$
 - d) Accept $\nu^{(k)} = \nu'$ with probability α , otherwise $\nu^{(k)} = \nu^{(k-1)}$

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Convergence and validity of the developed approach

The calculation presented was run with $N = 2000$ steps, with $M = 500$ samples drawn for the estimation of the marginalized likelihood at each step N . We wish to establish proper convergence of the samples. The trace plot of the chain together with its cumulative mean are shown in Figure 1, the x-axis representing the samples of the chain and the y-axis representing value and cumulative mean along the chain respectively.

The cumulative mean is used to assess convergence toward a stationary value. Following standard practice, a burn-in phase is performed by discarding the first 500 samples, which have not yet converged to the target posterior. After confirming proper convergence, the resulting posterior distribution is presented in Figure 2, alongside the prior distribution and a normal approximation of the samples.

The normalization coefficient associated with ν decreases to a value of 0.9989, corresponding to a 0.11% adjustment relative to the reference value. This adjustment is consistent with expectations, given

Figure 1. Trace plot and cumulative mean of the chain samples associated with the complete methodology

Figure 2. Prior distribution and adjusted posterior distribution estimated from converged samples

the overall positive reactivity biases of the studied mock-ups. The uncertainty on the parameter is

also reduced, from 0.5% to 0.16%. One must, however, keep in mind the under-estimation of certain input-parameter uncertainties such as the lattice pitch in the present case, which can lead to an under-estimation of the obtained uncertainty. Future work should ensure proper accounting of the technological parameters, even if it means over-estimating some parameters when necessary.

A normal approximation of the posterior distribution is shown in Figure 2 because of the normal prior distributions of the nuclear and technological parameters.

The obtained normalization coefficient can be applied to the parameter $\bar{\nu}_p$, and this new value can then be combined with $\bar{\nu}_d$ to compare the resulting $\bar{\nu}_{tot}$ with reference values from JEFF-3.1.1, JEFF-4, and the Neutron Data Standards 2018 [19] presented in Table IV.

Table IV. Comparison table of $\bar{\nu}_{tot}({}^{235}\text{U})$ at thermal energy $E_{th} = 0.0253 \text{ eV}$

Data source	$\bar{\nu}_{tot}$	Relative σ (%)
JEFF-3.1.1	2.436	0.71
Neutron Data Standards 2018	2.425	0.453
JEFF-4	2.437	0.56
Result obtained from this work	2.434	0.160

We observe a noticeable difference between the recommendations from the Neutron Data Standards 2018 and the JEFF values. The JEFF values, however, remain within the uncertainty range of the recommendations. This clearly demonstrates the benefit of assimilating integral-experiment results to reduce the uncertainties associated with these parameters that are critical for neutron simulations.

4.2. Posterior Predictive Check

The posterior predictive check (PPC) method can be used to assess the quality of a Bayesian model. It generates simulated data from the model's posterior predictive distribution. In this simple case we sample new simulated experimental biases using our converged chain to assess experimental-uncertainty-weighted average bias reduction.

Table V. Comparison of biases between prior and PPC-obtained distributions

Benchmarks	Prior biases	PPC-obtained biases	σ_{prior}	σ_{PPC}
EPICURE UH1.2	+468	+317	316	185
CAMELEON GC	+867	+716	381	190
CRISTO3	+518	+361	682	196
MISTRAL1	-100	-255	376	187
CRISTO1	-129	-284	381	219
CRISTO2 $C_B = 832 \text{ ppm}$	-183	-345	371	213
CRISTO2 "large"	-82	-241	371	213
ZPR HIC steel cladding	+120	-41	481	190
ZPR HIC aluminium cladding	-389	-559	481	187
Weighted average bias	142 pcm	-22 pcm		

Assuming normal distributions, we compare the sampled biases and uncertainties to the original results in Table V. The mean bias of the results obtained by PPC is indeed closer to the targeted values in reference safety studies (around 100 pcm). A larger number of steps N would allow an even tighter approach to the target value.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The approaches initially presented have been combined into a general methodology that allows us to incorporate the various sources of uncertainty while forgoing usual assumptions associated with analytical methods for the assimilation of integral-experiment data.

The resulting posterior yields a normalization factor ν of **0.9989** (-0.11% relative to the prior) and reduces the relative uncertainty of $\bar{\nu}_p$ from **0.5%** to **0.16%**. When combined with the delayed-neutron component $\bar{\nu}_d$, the total multiplicity $\bar{\nu}_{tot} = 2.434$ aligns with the JEFF-4 evaluation and lies well within the confidence intervals of the Neutron Data Standards 2018.

This approach was tested on a proof-of-principle case involving a single nuclear parameter and nine experimental benchmarks used for calibration. As with sample-based approaches generally, computational cost scales unfavorably with parameter dimensionality; the methodology is therefore designed for targeted assimilation problems with reduced dimensionality rather than as a substitute for large scale high-dimensionality adjustment more suited to GLS methods. The methodology will next be applied to ^{239}Pu resonance parameters using PST benchmarks from the ICSBEP database, a problem where the non-linear dependence of criticality on resonance widths and energies, combined with physical positivity constraints on these parameters, makes sample-based inference particularly appropriate.

Regarding future developments, each marginalization step is computationally expensive. Hamiltonian Monte-Carlo techniques, which exploit gradients to reduce autocorrelation, could decrease the number of samples required for convergence. Surrogate models for the forward simulation or the marginalization integral may offer additional speedups, though the trade-off between approximation accuracy and computational gain requires further investigation.

REFERENCES

- [1] Ivanov, E. "Nuclear data assimilation, scientific basis and current status". In: *EPJ N - Nuclear Sciences & Technologies* **7** (2021), 9. URL: <https://cea.hal.science/cea-03630697>.
- [2] Durán, I. "Looking for integral references for the fission cross sections in actinides above 1 MeV". In: *EPJ Web of Conferences* **294** (2024). Publisher: EDP Sciences, 04001. URL: https://www.epj-conferences.org/articles/epjconf/abs/2024/04/epjconf_wonder2024_04001/epjconf_wonder2024_04001.html.
- [3] Leeb, H. "Nuclear data evaluation: Status and perspectives". In: *EPJ Web of Conferences* **322** (2025). Ed. by Dimitriou, P., 10001. URL: <https://www.epj-conferences.org/10.1051/epjconf/202532210001>.
- [4] De Saint Jean, C. "On the use of Bayesian Monte-Carlo in evaluation of nuclear data". In: *EPJ Web of Conferences* **146** (2017). Ed. by Plompen, A., 02007. URL: <http://www.epj-conferences.org/10.1051/epjconf/201714602007>.
- [5] Siefman, D. "Stochastic vs. sensitivity-based integral parameter and nuclear data adjustments". In: *The European Physical Journal Plus* **133.10** (Oct. 1, 2018). Number: 10 Publisher: Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 429. URL: https://epjplus.epj.org/articles/epjplus/abs/2018/10/13360_2018_12303_Article/13360_2018_12303_Article.html.
- [6] Koning, A. "Bayesian monte carlo method for nuclear data evaluation". In: *Nuclear Data Sheets* **123** (Jan. 2015).

- [7] Rochman, D. "Monte Carlo nuclear data adjustment via integral information". In: *The European Physical Journal Plus* **133.12** (Dec. 2018), 537. URL: <http://link.springer.com/10.1140/epjp/i2018-12361-x>.
- [8] Sobes, V. *Users Guide to SAMINT: A Code for Nuclear Data Adjustment with SAMMY Based on Integral Experiments*. DP0902090, DPDP097, ORNL/TM-2014/245. Aug. 1, 2014, DP0902090, DPDP097, ORNL/TM-2014/245. URL: <https://www.osti.gov/biblio/1185560>.
- [9] De Saint Jean, C. "CONRAD – a code for nuclear data modeling and evaluation". In: *EPJ Nuclear Sciences & Technologies* **7** (2021), 10. URL: <https://www.epj-n.org/10.1051/epjn/2021011>.
- [10] Plompen, A. J. M., and, a. et al. "The joint evaluated fission and fusion nuclear data library, JEFF-3.3". In: *The European Physical Journal A* **56.7** (July 14, 2020), 181. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1140/epja/s10050-020-00141-9>.
- [11] Plompen, A. *The NEA High Priority Nuclear Data Request List for Future Needs*. JRC Publications Repository. 2008. URL: <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC47094>.
- [12] Santamarina, A. "Qualification of the APOLLO2.5/CEA93.V6 code for UOX and MOX fuelled PWRs - 5A-01". In: *Physor 2002*. Seoul (Korea, Republic of), Oct. 2002. URL: <https://inis.iaea.org/records/2hn9s-7hk76>.
- [13] Tamagno, P. "Marginalization methods for the production of conservative covariance on nuclear data". In: *EPJ Web of Conferences* **281** (2023). Ed. by Chiba, G., and Iwamoto, O., 00024. URL: <https://www.epj-conferences.org/10.1051/epjconf/202328100024>.
- [14] Song, C., and Kawai, R. "Monte Carlo and variance reduction methods for structural reliability analysis: A comprehensive review". In: *Probabilistic Engineering Mechanics* **73** (2023), 103479. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0266892023000681>.
- [15] Abyani, M., and Bahaari, M. R. "A comparative reliability study of corroded pipelines based on Monte Carlo Simulation and Latin Hypercube Sampling methods". In: *International Journal of Pressure Vessels and Piping* **181** (Mar. 1, 2020). Publisher: Elsevier, 104079. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0308016120300570>.
- [16] Palau, J.-M. "Accounting for statistical Monte-Carlo errors in Integral Data Assimilation". In: *BEPU 2024*. Tuscany, Italy, 2024, 13.
- [17] Terrazzoni, C. "Développement d'une méthodologie d'estimation d'erreurs dans les simulations neutroniques multi-échelles de réacteurs à eau de 3ème génération". PhD thesis. Aix-Marseille Université, 2024.
- [18] Chib, S., and Greenberg, E. "Understanding the Metropolis-Hastings Algorithm". In: *The American Statistician* **49.4** (Nov. 1, 1995), 327–335. URL: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/00031305.1995.10476177>.
- [19] Carlson, A. D. "Evaluation of the Neutron Data Standards". In: *Nuclear Data Sheets*. Special Issue on Nuclear Reaction Data **148** (Feb. 1, 2018), 143–188. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0090375218300218>.